

XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

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THE SIMPLE AND PROGRESSIV ASPECTS IN ENGLISH GRAMMAR: AN OVERVIEW

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Annotation: This thesis shed light on indefinite (simple) and progressive (continuous) aspects in English grammar and provides an overview, focusing on their definitions, forms, and functions. Initially the notion of “aspect”, as a category in English grammar, is discussed and Biber considers that state of completeness or non-completeness of the action or event as a crucial element of the aspect. On the other hand, according to Carter and McCarthy the aspect is the process of how the speaker perceives the duration of the events. Quirk distinguished four types of aspect and in this paper two of them: indefinite and continuous are discussed. The indefinite aspect is discussed as an action expressed without reference to their completeness or duration, typically used for facts, everyday actions and general truths. In contrast, progressive aspect emphasizes ongoing actions at a specific time.

Keywords: aspect, category, indefinite, progressive, tense.

Introduction. Aspect is a grammatical category of verb which indicates the manner in which the action is regarded, unlike *tense* which explores the exact time (past, present, future) the action occurred. The notion of “aspect” was firstly introduced at the beginning of nineteenth century from Latin language, the root of the word “*spect*” coming from the word “*spectare*” - “to see” – meaning “*how (something) looks*” (Boogaart, 2004). According to Carter and McCarthy (2006) in English, aspect is concerned mainly with how the speaker perceives the duration of events, and how different events relate to one another in time. However Biber considers aspect relates to considerations such as the completion or lack of completion of events or states described by a verb. Most of the learners conflate aspect and tense, however aspect is concerned with *how* an action unfolds over time – if it is ongoing, completed, habitual or repetitive.

INDEFINITE ASPECT. Quirk et al (2005) distinguished the aspect types, presenting two sets of aspectual contrasts. These aspectual contrasts are: progressive (continuous) versus non-progressive (simple / indefinite) and perfective versus non-perfective. The indefinite or some say simple aspect is based on the plain form of the verb and marked in these case:

- 1) Third singular form of the verb in Present Simple tense:
 - a) -s after verbs ending in vowels or voiced consonants;e.g. She plays / He comes

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b) –es after verbs ending in –s, -ss, -sh, -ch, -x, -z, -o;

e.g. She passes / It goes

c) –ies after verbs ending in –y with preceding consonant change ;

e.g. try – tries / study – studies

2) Regular form of the verb in Past Simple tense is marked with –ed

e.g. I played

3) In the Future tense indefinite form is built up by means of the auxiliary verbs “will” and “shall”

e.g. I will do exercises tomorrow / we shall go cinema.

The Indefinite aspective category is used to state the actions which (will) occur(ed) every day, take place once and the result is obvious and true facts that nobody can reject.

PROGRESSIVE ASPECT. Blokh describes the aspective category of progressive as a “category of development” and it is constituted by the opposition of the continuous forms of the verb to the indefinite forms of the verb. The marked member of opposition is built up by the auxiliary –be and present participle of the conjugated verb. The “progressive” discloses the nature of development of the verbal action, on which ground the suggested name for the category as a whole will be “development” (M.Y. Blokh, 2006). Although there are some other thoughts about this: “With the progressive aspect, the focus is principally on the duration of the event. It may therefore be used to indicate that something is ongoing, unfinished, or that it is extended but temporary. It may indicate that something is/was/ will be in progress when something else happens/happened. In other words, the focus is not on the starting or finishing point of an event, but on the event as seen from its centre” (Carter & McCarthy, 2006). The morphemes that build progressive aspect might vary in different tenses as written below:

1. In Present Tense auxiliary verbs “am/is/are” are put between Subject and Verb, with inflection –ing adjoining to the “verb”.

e.g. I am reading a book now.

She is running at the moment.

Children are playing in the ground currently.

In Present tense present-time expressing words are used to refer the period of the event. They are: right now, now, at the moment, currently. These words are the indicators which showcase the presence of Present Continuous tense.

2. In Past Tense progressive aspect is made by putting auxiliary verbs “was/were” before the Verb + ing.

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e.g. I was washing the dishes yesterday.

They were coming back home that moment.

In this tense time markers are quite different than in Present tense. They are considered as tense indicators and not only used for only Past Continuous, but also for all Past tense: yesterday, the day before yesterday, last day/week/month/season/year/century, ago. The one phrase is the only exception – at that moment - being a time marker for only Past Continuous.

3. In Future Tense by auxiliary verbs “will” and “be” being exerted after Subject and before Verb+ing, in the exact order.

e.g. I will be travelling around the world next year.

Susan will be studying at university tomorrow.

The case abovementioned is also the same for Future tense. The time indicators of this aspectual category are tomorrow, tonight, next year/month/week/day etc. This very type of aspectual category is not only used as “continuum”, but also it refers a tense. Structure of Present Continuous tense can function as a Future tense action in certain cases: 1) the future action which is already settled or planned (e.g. I am going away tonight); 2) fixed and obvious action, which in the near future takes place (e.g. She must go, she is meeting with Jack). The both of the cases are used for future intentions and marked with future indicating words. For example, “tomorrow”, “tonight”, “this time” etc. but in the latter’s case omitting of such words has minimal impact to the meaning as it is understood by the context (Gordon & Krylova, 1980).

Conclusion. In summary, the simple aspect in English grammar is used to convey general facts and habitual actions without emphasis on duration, while the progressive aspect highlights actions that are ongoing at a specific time. The primary difference between the two lies in their focus: the simple aspect presents actions as complete units, whereas the progressive aspect emphasizes their duration and continuity. A clear understanding of these aspects is essential for mastering English grammar, as it allows speakers to convey timing and context accurately. Overall, the ability to distinguish and use simple and progressive aspects effectively is a fundamental skill for achieving proficiency in English.

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